

Infrared Spectra and Thermal Studies of Some Reported Heteropoly Complexes

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In this short communication thermal behaviour and infrared spectral analysis of five different heteropoly complexes namely, ammonium-12 heteropoly vanadomolybdate, $(\text{NH}_4)_{10}[\text{MoV}_{12}\text{O}_{42}] \cdot 20\text{H}_2\text{O}$, ammonium-6 heteropoly vanadotungstate, $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{W}_6\text{O}_{19}] \cdot 11\text{H}_2\text{O}$, potassium-6 heteropoly vanadomolybdate, $\text{K}_2[\text{MoV}_6\text{O}_{18}] \cdot 11\text{H}_2\text{O}$, ammonium-10 heteropoly vanadocobaltate, $(\text{NH}_4)_4[\text{CoV}_{10}\text{V}_{20}] \cdot 18\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and ammonium-12 heteropoly vanadoantimonate, $(\text{NH}_4)_7[\text{SbV}_{12}\text{O}_{42}] \cdot 23\text{H}_2\text{O}$ have been discussed.

The compounds have been synthesised and analysed as reported earlier¹⁻⁴. Thermal stability studies on the heteropoly compounds prepared were conducted^{5,6} by thermogravimetric analysis (tga), differential thermal analysis (dta) and by heating at fixed temperatures followed by solubility determinations of the heated materials to ascertain decomposition. All dta and tga experiments were done at a heating rate of 5°/min. The heating at fixed temperatures was performed in air in a muffle furnace. To ascertain decomposition due to heating, the heated sample (2-3 g) was placed in 50 ml of water and stirred for 0.5 hr. Degree of insolubility of sample was taken as measure of stability. The weight loss employed to calculate the amount of water or ammonia lost was based on static heating experiments rather than tga results. The former were considered to be more accurate since larger samples weighing 2 to 3 g were taken. Complete analysis of the compound was carried out after the decomposition temperature to ascertain the final decomposition of the compounds into the lower oxides of the constituent atoms. All tga data on heteropoly vanadates and heteropoly molybdates show weight loss above 650° but this corresponds to slow volatilization of vanadium pentoxide and molybdenum trioxide, respectively.

Ammonium-12 vanadomolybdate is stable at 300° as is shown by its complete solubility in water. The dta data for this hydrate show unresolved endotherms from 25 to 245°. This correlates well with the tga data where the bulk of water as well as ammonia is lost upto this point. From thereon, the compound slowly decomposes by losing water or ammonia. At 350°, the compound is partly stable but the change is complete at 400° where the heteropoly complex breaks completely by losing 4 moles of water (or ammonia). Breakage of the heteropoly cage is confirmed by chemical analysis as well as the dta data which show exotherms at 400-420°.

Ammonium-6 vanadotungstate loses all its water of hydration and ammonia till 300°. The

heteropoly cage $[\text{W}_6\text{O}_{19}]^{2-}$ is stable at this temperature as it is completely soluble in water. This heteropoly complex breaks at 350° as is shown by its complete insolubility in water. DTA data corroborate the above result. Thermal stability of potassium-6 vanadomolybdate tallies closely with ammonium-6 vanadotungstate.

Ammonium-10 vanadocobaltate loses bulk of its water and ammonia till 200°. The static heating experiments for this salt show a loss of 20%. The tga results show a loss of 19.9% between 25 and 200°, the theoretical being 20.3% corresponding to the loss of 16 molecules of water or ammonia. Between 200 and 400° there is a plateau in the tga showing little loss of weight. A sudden break in tga curve near 400° shows a loss of 7.5% against the theoretical loss of 7.9% corresponding to the loss of 6 molecules of water or ammonia. The heteropoly complex also breaks at 400° as confirmed by dta data showing exotherms at 390-415°.

Ammonium-12 vanadoantimonate loses all its water of hydration as well as ammonia till 400° and it breaks at 450°. So, the thermal stability of the heteropoly cage $[\text{SbV}_{12}\text{O}_{42}]^{7-}$ is 400°. The ammonium salts can loose ammonia as well as water and thermal analysis alone cannot distinguish this possibility⁷.

Infrared spectra of some heteropoly compounds have been examined by Tsigdinos⁸, Brown⁹ and Sharpless *et al*¹⁰. Infrared spectra of the above mentioned heteropoly compounds in KBr pellets have been recorded from 4000 to 400 cm⁻¹ on a grating IR spectrophotometer, Perkin-Elmer Model 577. Results are given in Table 1. The peaks at 3500-3300 and 3180-3130 cm⁻¹ region (antisymmetric and symmetric O-H stretching mode¹¹) correspond to those of water¹². The peaks at 1620-1600 cm⁻¹ are also attributed to water (H-O-H bending mode¹³). Lattice water also absorbs in the lower frequency region (600-300 cm⁻¹) owing to librational modes^{12,13}. The sharp peaks at 1420-1390 cm⁻¹ may be attributed to the presence of N-H bond¹⁴. Deformative frequency of the ammonium ion is also known to be active in 3300-3100 cm⁻¹ region. So, the broad bands shown by these compounds in the 3500-3100 cm⁻¹ region may be due to lattice water as well as ammonium ion. Probable assignments¹⁵⁻¹⁷ for other peaks are 1000-900 cm⁻¹ (sharp) for M-O and 800-750 cm⁻¹ due to M-O-M bridging (M=V, Mo or W). In the case of interacted heteropoly complexes of V, Mo and W, the absorption due to central metal octahedron may be masked by the absorption of metal oxygen linkage of the surrounding metal octahedra. Absorption due to Co-O linkage has been reported¹⁸ in the lower frequency region 450-430 cm⁻¹. So, in the case of $(\text{NH}_4)_4[\text{CoV}_{10}\text{O}_{38}] \cdot 18\text{H}_2\text{O}$, the broad band at 442 cm⁻¹ may be due to Co-O absorption of the central octahedron as well as lattice water. Sb-O absorbs below 400 cm⁻¹ and therefore could not be observed in the ir. Infrared spectra of the ignited

NOTES

TABLE 1—INFRARED ABSORPTION FREQUENCIES (cm⁻¹) OF HETEROPOLY COMPOUNDS

(NH ₄) ₁₀ [MoV ₁₂ O ₃₈]20H ₂ O	9480b 3140b	1615m	1400s	935s 915s	800s 715s	560s 410m
Ignited sample (400°)	—	—	—	910s 890s	—	—
(NH ₄) ₈ [WV ₆ O ₁₈]11H ₂ O	3445b 3170b	1605b	1405b	975s 980s	840b 755m	600s 410s
Ignited sample (350°)	—	—	—	910s 940s	—	—
K ₂ [MoV ₆ O ₁₈]11H ₂ O	3440s	1610m	—	940s	805s 720s	580s
Ignited sample (350°)	—	—	—	910s	—	—
(NH ₄) ₄ [CoV ₁₀ O ₃₀]18H ₂ O	3180b	1615m	1410m	960s	850b 780b	600b 442b
Ignited sample (400°)	—	—	—	980	—	442s
(NH ₄) ₇ [SbV ₁₂ O ₃₆]28H ₂ O	3485b 3175b	—	1890s	1000s 975s	745s	600s 455m
Ignited sample (450°)	—	—	—	915s 945s	—	—

s = sharp, m = medium, b = broad.

samples were also taken. The decomposition temperature of the heteropoly complexes was taken as the ignition temperature. The peaks, characteristic of lattice water as well as ammonium ion were not found. The observed peaks confirmed the breakage of heteropoly complexes into the lower oxides of their constituent atoms.

Potential Local Anaesthetic Agents. Part-III :
Alkylaryl aminoacetyl-2-aminothiazoles
and Benzimidazoles

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THE essential structural requirements for anaestheticophore group in local anaesthetics seems to be a lipophilic moiety containing an aromatic nucleus, an intermediate alkyl or aryl substituted chain and a hydrophilic end consisting of a tertiary amino group¹⁻⁴. The thiazole and imidazole groups are of great importance in biological systems⁵⁻¹⁰. The title compounds appear to possess all the necessary structural requirements for local anaesthetic agent. Therefore, it was thought worthwhile to synthesise some alkylaryl-aminoacetyl-2-aminothiazoles and benzimidazoles by the condensation of chloroacetylchloride with 2-aminothiazole/benzimidazole followed by treatment with various primary and secondary amines.

The structures of these compounds have been established on the basis of their analysis and infrared spectrum. IR spectra of these compounds show characteristic strong absorption peaks at 1650-1625 cm⁻¹ and 1370-1360 cm⁻¹ corresponding to C=O and C-N bands, respectively. An

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